

What is sobat ambisius ?

Sobat Ambisius is an online education site founded in 2021, we aim to provide education and tutorials for free. We will always create actual, quality and reliable content. We are based in Jakarta, Indonesia.

Here we will provide the vision, mission, and goals of this site:

Vision

Become a site that is able to provide useful information and can help others.

Mission

1. Provide quality content in an easy-to-understand language style.
2. Contribute to the field of education and technology for the general public.
3. Provide a survey questionnaire that serves to receive all criticisms and suggestions from the public.

Purpose

1. Improving the quality of learning for the community through the use of the internet.
2. Strive to create content that is efficient, effective, and easily understood by the public.
3. Donate 15% of the income generated by this site for people in need.